

Entropy as non-workable energy: an easy engineering interpretation for teaching thermodynamics in engineering degree courses

Fernando Varela Díez^{1,*}, Susana Sánchez-Orgaz², Mercedes Ibarra Mollá¹, José Daniel Marcos del Cano¹, Alicia Mayoral Esteban¹

¹ Dept. of Energy Engineering, Universidad Nacional de Educación a Distancia (UNED), C/ Juan del Rosal 12, 28040 Madrid, Spain, Phone: +34-91-3986468

² Dept. of Energy Engineering Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, José Gutiérrez Abascal, 28006, Madrid, Spain, Phone: +34-91-0677191

* fvarela@ind.uned.es

1. Introduction

The introduction of the second law of thermodynamics necessitates the discussion of entropy, a concept that often requires clarification for students. In pedagogical practice, entropy is frequently described as "disorder" to facilitate comprehension. However, this analogy originates from statistical thermodynamics, a framework that is typically beyond the scope of undergraduate curricula and of limited utility in engineering applications. Consequently, students often perceive entropy as an abstract quantity used primarily for verifying the second law in engineering system analyses rather than as a physically meaningful property.

This study proposes an alternative pedagogical approach to enhance students' conceptual understanding of entropy, particularly in the context of engineering applications.

Although the interpretation proposed here has been briefly mentioned in some texts (see [1], [2], [3]), it has neither been justified nor developed in any of them, thus failing to take advantage of its pedagogical approach. Zemansky [4] does a similar work but considering the variation of entropy in the universe instead of the system, which is our purpose.

2. The concept of "workable energy"

Consider the **maximum total work** that can be extracted from a closed system under given pressure and temperature (P, T) conditions in a process that brings it to the dead state (P_0, T_0), **including work done against the atmosphere**.

The energy balance of the system is given by:

$$U_0 - E = Q + W \quad [1]$$

The entropy balance for the surroundings is:

$$\Delta S_{amb} = \frac{-Q}{T_0} \quad [2]$$

The entropy balance for the universe is:

$$\Delta S_u = \Delta S + \Delta S_{amb} = (S_0 - S) + \frac{-Q}{T_0} = \sigma + \sigma_Q \quad [3]$$

By combining these equations, the energy balance can be expressed as:

$$U_0 - E = T_0(S_0 - S) - T_0(\sigma + \sigma_Q) - W \quad [4]$$

Thus, the work **produced** in the process is:

$$-W = (E - U_0) - T_0(S - S_0) - T_0(\sigma + \sigma_Q) \quad [5]$$

or equivalently:

$$-W = (E - U_0) - T_0(S - S_0) - I \quad [6]$$

Since the total irreversibility I is always positive, the maximum extractable work is:

$$-W_{\max} = (E - U_0) - T_0(S - S_0) \quad [7]$$

This expression differs slightly from the definition of exergy, as it explicitly accounts for the work done against the atmosphere. Although this work cannot be utilized, it still is work extracted from the energy of the system and therefore corresponds to high-quality energy.

Similar to exergy, this quantity is a state function, which we define as **workable energy** E_w - energy convertible into work:

$$E_w = (E - U_0) - T_0(S - S_0) \quad [8]$$

This function represents the portion of a system's energy that is convertible into work and therefore can be interpreted as **high quality energy**. The corresponding specific function is

$$e_w = (e - u_0) + T_0(s - s_0) \quad [9]$$

By analogy with energy, we define **non-workable energy** E_{nw} as the portion of a system's energy that cannot be converted into work under any circumstances (low quality energy):

$$\begin{aligned} E_{nw} &= E - E_w = U_0 + T_0(S - S_0) \\ e_{nw} &= e - e_w = u_0 + T_0(s - s_0) \end{aligned} \quad [10]$$

Applying this concept to any process in a closed system, we obtain:

$$\Delta E_{nw} = \Delta E - \Delta E_w = T_0 \cdot \Delta S \quad [11]$$

$$\Delta S = \frac{\Delta E_{nw}}{T_0} \quad \Delta s = \frac{\Delta e_{nw}}{T_0} \quad de_{nw} = T_0 \cdot ds \quad [12]$$

In open systems, where the system's mass is variable, applying the same concept,

$$\frac{dE_{nw}}{dt} = \frac{dU_0}{dt} + T_0 \frac{d(S - S_0)}{dt} = u_0 \frac{dm}{dt} + T_0 \left(m \frac{ds}{dt} + s \frac{dm}{dt} - s_0 \frac{dm}{dt} \right) = e_{nw} \cdot \frac{dm}{dt} + T_0 \cdot m \frac{ds}{dt} \quad [13]$$

As

$$\frac{dE_{nw}}{dt} = e_{nw} \frac{dm}{dt} + m \frac{de_{nw}}{dt} \quad [14]$$

We obtain

$$m \frac{de_{nw}}{dt} = T_0 \cdot m \frac{ds}{dt} \quad \frac{de_{nw}}{dt} = T_0 \cdot \frac{ds}{dt} \quad de_{nw} = T_0 \cdot ds \quad [15]$$

Thus, an increase in entropy corresponds to an increase in the system's non-workable energy per unit of ambient temperature. Consequently, **the increase in entropy in a process is directly proportional to an increase in non-workable energy within the system.**

The behaviour of entropy is tied to the behaviour of low-quality energy, but not directly to that of the high-quality energy. In other words, a rise in entropy means low-quality energy increase, but high quality energy can decrease (or increase, or remain constant depend on the case). In the next section we will analyse this behaviour to illustrate this fact.

3. Understanding the entropy variation in closed systems

Let us now analyse the entropy variation of a closed system from the workable energy point of view.

Case a) In Isolated systems, energy is preserved, and entropy always increases due to the second principle:

$$\Delta E = 0 \quad \Delta S = \sigma \geq 0 \quad [16]$$

So

$$\Delta E_{nw} = T_0 \Delta S \geq 0 \quad \Delta E_w = \Delta E - \Delta E_{nw} \leq 0 \quad [17]$$

In this case, the **increase in entropy in the system reflects directly the destruction of workable energy**, which is converted directly into non-workable energy, representing a degradation of the system's energy.

Fig. 1. Entropy increase in an isolated system

Case b). If the system is not isolated, the following scenarios may occur:

$\Delta E > 0; \Delta S > 0.$ Isolated volumetric compressor with friction. $\Delta E_{nw} = T_0 \Delta S \geq 0$ $\Delta E_w = \Delta E - \Delta E_{nw} \quad \text{undefined}$	
$\Delta E > 0; \Delta S = 0$ Isolated volumetric compressor without friction. $\Delta E_{nw} = T_0 \Delta S = 0$ $\Delta E_w = \Delta E > 0$	
$\Delta E > 0; \Delta S < 0.$ Non-isolated volumetric compressor with heat rejection. $(W + Q > 0)$ $\Delta E_{nw} = T_0 \Delta S < 0$ $\Delta E_w = \Delta E - \Delta E_{nw} > 0$	
$\Delta E < 0; \Delta S < 0.$ Uninsulated DHW tank: Heat rejection. $\Delta E_{nw} = T_0 \Delta S < 0$ $\Delta E_w = \Delta E - \Delta E_{nw} \quad \text{undefined}$	

<p>$\Delta E < 0; \Delta S > 0.$ Expansion in an isolated piston with friction.</p> $\Delta E_{nw} = T_0 \Delta S > 0$ $\Delta E_w = \Delta E - \Delta E_{nw} < 0$	
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4. Assessing the effectiveness of the proposed pedagogical approach

We would perform an experimental study using a Randomized Controlled Trial (RCT) design.

4.1 Procedure

Students will be randomly divided into two groups:

- Group A (Control): Will receive the traditional explanation of entropy (e.g., based on formal definitions from the second law of thermodynamics).
- Group B (Experimental): Will receive the new explanation (e.g., using visual analogies, interactive simulations, or models inspired by information theory).

4.2 Assessment Instruments

- Pre-test: A test covering basic thermodynamics concepts administered before the intervention to ensure similar baseline knowledge across groups.
- Intervention: Delivery of the two different teaching methods.
- Post-test: A specific test on entropy, including theoretical questions and application problems.
- Perception Survey: A questionnaire assessing students' perceived clarity, motivation, and understanding.

4.3 Data Analysis

- Post-test scores will be compared between groups using an independent samples t-test.
- Survey responses will be analyzed to evaluate subjective perceptions of the teaching methods.

4.4 Success Criteria

- The experimental group should demonstrate a statistically significant improvement in understanding and applying the concept of entropy.
- Higher levels of perceived clarity and satisfaction as indicated in the survey responses.

5. Conclusions

Through the development of the concept of non-workable energy, a macroscopic interpretation of the concept of entropy (specifically, its variation) has been identified, with potential applications in engineering education.

In recent years, it has been observed that the use of this interpretation help undergraduate engineering students understand the concept of entropy, providing an engineering-based interpretation that is relatively easy to comprehend.

6. References

- [1] Klein, J.F., Physical significance of entropy or of the second law, The Scientific Press, 1910.
- [2] Kostic, M. J., The Elusive Nature of Entropy and Its Physical Meaning. Entropy, 2014. 16: p. 953-967.
- [3] Wu, J. Understanding entropy through a discussion of exergy. European Journal of Physics, 2020. 41: 19p
- [4] Zemansky, M. W., Dittman, R. H., Heat and Thermodynamics. McGraw Hill, 1981.